

1 ORGANIC CARBON ENRICHMENT IN SEDIMENTS: EFFECTS OF RAINFALL
2 CHARACTERISTICS UNDER DIFFERENT LAND USES IN A MEDITERRANEAN
3 AREA.

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11 **Abstract**

12 The results of an experiment to evaluate the effect of rainfall characteristics on organic
13 carbon (OC) losses and on the type of particles mobilized by erosion under natural
14 rainfall and under different land uses (non-disturbed forested area, and a non-irrigated
15 olive cropland) at plot scale are presented. Labile (particulate organic carbon, POC) and
16 stable (mineral associated organic carbon, MOC) carbon pools were measured in soil
17 and sediments. Based on the product of total rainfall and I₃₀ (mm mmh⁻¹), as a measure
18 of rainfall erosivity, events were divided into three classes (from low to high erosivity).
19 A positive correlation between P*I₃₀ and OC concentration (r=0.54, p<0.01) and P*I₃₀
20 and OC enrichment ratios (r=0.43, p<0.05) was observed for the forest plot, while no
21 correlation and even a negative trend between both variables was observed in the olive
22 plot. These opposite responses are due to the effect that vegetation cover had on
23 aggregate soil stability and on OC mobilization and transport through the plot. With
24 high intensity storms the high sediment removal in the olive plot led to subsoil and
25 topsoil becoming mixed reducing the overall nutrient and OC concentration of the

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eroded sediment. Enrichment ratios of OC (ER_{OC}) were higher in the olive than in the forest plot in events of low rainfall erosivity (class 1), which represented almost 50% of the total events occurring in this area, while the differences between plots as regards total mobilized OC were greater after high rainfall erosivity events, until up to three times more carbon being mobilized in the olive plot compared with the forest one. POC transport in sediments was higher in the olive plots and was more likely to occur in events of low intensity. MOC was transported in high intensity events: in aggregate form with a greater probability of being sequestered in the sediment (aggregates smaller than 20 μm) or in particulate form (after the rupture of aggregates) with a greater probability of mineralization.

37 Erosion-induced carbon loss, soil aggregates, organic carbon pools, rainfall erosivity,
38 semi-arid.

39 **1. Introduction**

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41 Water erosion is an important contributor to carbon redistribution in terrestrial
42 landscapes and export to aquatic systems (Jacinthe et al., 2004). The overall impact of
43 human-induced erosion on the carbon cycle remains controversial (Lal, 1995) and any
44 assessment of this impact depends on the scale at which erosion is considered
45 (vanNoordwijk et al., 1999). A great variability in the OC enrichment ratio (ER) values
46 have been found in the literature. OC enrichment ratios of between 1.5 and 3 have been
47 recorded (Palis et al., 1997; Starr et al., 2000; Martínez-Mena et al., 2002, Jin et al.,
48 2008) but even values of 5 have been observed in some soils initially poor in SOC
49 (Avnimelech and Mchenry, 1984). According to Palis et al., (1997) and Polyakov and
50 Lal, (2004) higher ER may also result from the non-homogeneous distribution of

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51 nutrients among particles of various sizes. ER also tends to be higher for more
52 aggregated soils with high concentrations of clay than less aggregated and coarse-
53 textured soils.

54 From all these studies it is clear that suspended sediment is enriched in OC, particularly
55 at plot scale, but the extent to which rainfall characteristics are responsible for this
56 enrichment mechanism is still unclear. Such knowledge could be useful for modelling
57 OC losses, since, at present many models use constant values for ER or equations that
58 relate ER to average soil loss during a rainfall event or a whole year.

59 Different results concerning to the relationships between rainfall characteristics and C
60 mobilization by erosion processes have been found in the literature (Strickland et al.,
61 2005, Truman et al., 2007, Polyakov and Lal, 2004, Jacinthe et al., 2004, Jin et al.,
62 2009).. Overall, the rainfall characteristics most closely related to OC mobilization are
63 rainfall intensity and rainfall duration. Thus, some authors have found higher OC
64 content in the sediments transported during low-intensity storms than in the material
65 displaced during high-intensity storms (Jacinthe et al., 2004, Palis et al., 1994,
66 Bajracharya et al., 1998, Schiettecatte et al., 2008), while others have pointed to the
67 greater contribution of high erosive events, which have enough energy to detach and
68 transport particles to which nutrients are bound (Ramos et al., 2006). The differences
69 between constant and variable rainfall within the storm have also been studied.
70 Strickland et al., (2005) found much higher peak C loss rates and enrichment ratios
71 during the first half of variable events than during constant rainfall intensity events.
72 Frauenfeld and Truman, (2004) suggested that total sediment loss is transport-limited
73 under constant intensity events, and both detachment and transport-limited under
74 variable intensity events. Other authors suggested that sediment will become less
75 enriched in carbon as time passes during an event since the more carbon-rich fine

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76 aggregates are depleted early in the event (Wan and El-Swaify, 1998, Palis et al., 1997,
77 Polyakov and Lal, 2004, Jin et al., 2009). All these findings stress the importance of
78 short, high intensity storms in which carbon loss through erosion may be facilitated
79 (Strickland et al., 2005).
80 ER_{OC} in sediment is often attributed to poorly decomposed non-cohesive plant
81 fragments (Ghadiri and Rose, 1991), which, despite their relatively low concentration in
82 the soil, are transported preferentially due to their low density. In this way, Jacinthe et
83 al., (2004) showed that the C mobilized during low intensity rainfall was 2.5 times more
84 labile than the C released during high-energy storms. According to Polyakov and Lal
85 (2008), of all SOC displaced by erosion, up to 44% is lost from the watershed to the
86 aquatic system, and, of the 56% remaining in the watershed, 15% has the potential to be
87 mineralised. These authors observed a relationship between mineralization ratios and
88 the aggregate size. Thus, they found that aggregates between 0.5 and 1.0 mm displayed
89 mineralization ratios nine times higher than those smaller than 0.050 mm. Furthermore,
90 they related this behaviour to the non-homogeneous distribution of labile C within the
91 aggregates, C concentration being lower in macro than in microaggregates, and to the
92 different degree of physical protection offered within the aggregates. Losses of C from
93 macroaggregates are usually more rapid than those from microaggregates due to the
94 lower protective effect of biophysical and chemical processes (Jastro & Miller, 1998).
95 Furthermore, the OC that binds microaggregates to form macroaggregates is a labile
96 fraction and is highly sensitive to land use change and cultivation (Shrestha et al.,
97 2007). A review of the available literature indicates that different land uses have a
98 strong effect on soil properties, especially aggregation and SOC dynamics. The
99 conversion of soil from forest to other land uses results in higher bulk density, lower
100 hydraulic conductivity, and a greater susceptibility to erosion (Lal, 2003), thereby

101 exacerbating soil degradation and the decline in SOC concentration (Lal and Kimble,
102 1997). The organic matter losses resulting from the cultivation of native land in a wide
103 range of climatic conditions and for a different number of years following the
104 conversion have been reported in the literature (Voroney et al., 1981, Schlesinger, 1986,
105 Malo et al., 2005). However, there is a paucity of information regarding the mechanisms
106 and magnitudes of SOC associated with aggregate- and particle-size fractions under
107 different land uses (Shrestha et al., 2007).

108 Most studies that relate OC enrichment ratios, rainfall characteristics and type of
109 transported particles have been carried out with simulated rainfall, both in the laboratory
110 (Jacinthe et al., 2002, Polyakov and Lal, 2004, Stricland et al., 2005, Jin et al., 2009)
111 and in the field (Truman et al., 2007, Jin et al., 2008). The problem obtained within
112 these approaches is the representativeness of field conditions and the extent to which the
113 data obtained with these microcosms can be extrapolated. Thus, field monitoring under
114 natural rainfall conditions and during long periods can help to develop diagnostic
115 models that will improve our understanding of the underlying mechanisms and
116 processes affecting erosion-induced losses of SOC. Furthermore, if this type of study is
117 conducted across a range of climatic conditions we can improve our ability to assess the
118 impact of water erosion on the global C cycle (Jacinthe et al., 2004) and thus to
119 elucidate to what extent soil erosion should be considered a net carbon source or sink.

120 In a previous study (Martínez-Mena et al., 2008), we detected a significant increase in
121 the total OC mobilized by erosion due to land use change from forest to cultivated
122 areas. In the present study we focus in analysing the effect of the rainfall characteristics
123 on the type of particles mobilized by erosion and the associated OC at plot scale and
124 under different land uses. We hypothesize that changing land use from forest to
125 agriculture induces changes in soil conditions, especially soil structure. Those changes

126 together with the rainfall characteristics will affect the mobilization of soil organic
127 carbon by erosion processes.

128 **2. Material and methods**

129 **2.1. Study area**

130 The study area was located in Cehegin in the northwest of the province of Murcia (S.E.
131 Spain) at an altitude ranges from 600 to 800 m.a.s.l. The climate is semi-arid with an
132 average annual precipitation of 300 mm, concentrated in the spring and autumn months.
133 The mean annual temperature is relatively high, 16.6°C, and mean potential
134 evapotranspiration reaches 800 mm yr⁻¹, so the long-term water deficit, calculated by
135 the Thornthwaite method, is 500 mm. July and August are the driest months. These
136 conditions result in an aridic soil moisture and thermic soil temperature regime
137 (ICONA, 1988).

138 This area is representative of the agricultural, socio-economic and environmental
139 situation of many dry land farming areas in the region, where the main limitation to
140 agricultural development is the shortage of water. A heterogeneous mosaic of
141 agricultural practices exists in this area. Two land uses were selected to carry out the
142 study: 1) non-disturbed forest area, and 2) a non-irrigated olive grove without terraces
143 and ploughed following the contour lines. This cultivated area has been used for 100
144 years, while the forest area is covered by a typical Mediterranean semi-arid shrubland
145 with scattered Aleppo pines (*Pinus halepensis* Mill.). The soils, derived from limestone
146 coluvium, are classified as Petric calcisol (WRB) in the forest area, and Hypercalcic
147 calcisol ((WRB) in the cultivated area. The two areas are adjacent and located on a
148 glaxis hillslope with a mean slope of 10-12%, with good drainage and a high percentage
149 of surface stones. Because both areas are located on soils developed from the same
150 parent materials and are exposed to the same climatic conditions, the difference in soil

151 properties were assumed to be primarily attributed to land use and cultivation. More
152 details of soil characteristics can be seen in Martínez-Mena et al., (2008).

153 **2.2. Analytical methods and computation**

154 **2.2.1. Soil OC analysis**

155 Soil samples were collected in October 2005 from the surface layer (0-0.05 m), in
156 twenty randomly distributed sampling points in each land use area to determine total
157 soil organic carbon (OC), particulate organic carbon (POC) and mineral bound organic
158 carbon (MOC). All determinations were made in the bulk soil ($< 2000\mu\text{m}$) and in the
159 large macroaggregates ($5000-2000\ \mu\text{m}$), small macroaggregates ($2000-250\mu\text{m}$),
160 microaggregates ($250-50\ \mu\text{m}$) and silt-plus clay-size particles ($<50\ \mu\text{m}$) obtained by the
161 dry sieving method.

162 POC and MOC were determined from 20 grams of dry mineral soil from each of the
163 aggregate sizes selected, after dispersing by shaking overnight in a 100-ml solution of
164 sodium hexametaphosphate ($5\ \text{g l}^{-1}$) and sieving through a $0.050\ \text{mm}$ sieve. The POC
165 ($\geq 0.050\ \text{mm}$) was recovered by back-washing the sieve followed by filtration (Whatman
166 filter paper #541). POC consisted of free organic debris and some larger fragments of
167 organic matter released by dispersion from the soil aggregates. The MOC fraction
168 ($< 0.050\ \text{mm}$) was recovered by evaporation. MOC consisted of soil C associated with
169 silt and clay size particles and some smaller fragments of organic matter released by
170 dispersion of the soil aggregates. Both fractions were weighed after oven drying (60°C),
171 ground using a mortar and stored for carbon analysis.

172 Organic carbon from the bulk soil and ground organic carbon from the POC and MOC
173 separation were determined by wet oxidation using a hot mixture of 1 N potassium
174 dichromate and concentrated sulphuric acid, according to the Yeomans & Bremner 's
175 method (1989). Soil C in the POC or MOC fraction ($\text{g C g}^{-1}\ \text{soil}$) was calculated by

176 multiplying the dry mass of each part (g part g^{-1} soil) by the respective C concentration
177 (g C g^{-1} part).

178 **2.2.2. Soil Aggregate stability**

179 To assess the effect of land use change on aggregate stability, a drop impact test (TDI)
180 was applied. The stability was determined with a burette nozzle with silicon tubing
181 together with a supply system with a constant head. The drops produced with distilled
182 water had a weight of 0.1 g. The water drops were allowed to fall through a polythene
183 pipe from 1 m height onto twenty air-dried aggregates of 3-5 mm placed on a 2 mm
184 sieve. The test consisted of measuring the weight of aggregates passing through a > 2
185 mm mesh after applying ten drops (Imeson and Vis, 1984).

186 **2.2.3. Sediment analysis**

187 Runoff and sediment (from September 2005 to June 2009) were collected from two
188 closed erosion plots (8 m large x 2 m width) after each rainfall event. Sampling of the
189 sediments collecting in a tank was carried out after thorough stirring. Five aliquots of 1
190 L were taken from different depths. The sediment was filtered, oven-dried at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$,
191 weighed to determine the suspended sediment concentration and stored for C
192 determination. The sediment concentrations were averaged and multiplied by the total
193 runoff to calculate total soil loss. For those events producing sufficient sediment, POC
194 and MOC were measured in addition to total OC.

195 Total OC export during a rainfall event was computed as the product of soil loss (g soil
196 loss) and sediment C concentration (g C kg^{-1}). The methodology used to analyse total
197 OC, POC and MOC in sediments was the same as that used for the bulk soil.

198 The sediment samples collected were immediately carried to the laboratory to determine
199 the size distribution of the effective (nondispersed) sediment using a Coulter LS200
200 laser diffraction device (Florida, USA). After determining the size distribution of the

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201 effective sediment, subsamples were treated with hydrogen peroxide to remove organic
202 matter before being dispersed in sodium hexametaphosphate and using ultrasonic
203 dispersion. The ultimate (dispersed) particle sized was measured, as well, using the
204 Coulter LS200 laser diffraction equipment.

205 A comparison of the effective particle size composition with the ultimate particle size of
206 the transported sediment can be used as an aggregation index and thus can give an idea
207 of the form in which the sediment is transported (as aggregate or as a primary particle).

208 A rain gauge connected to a data logger was installed to measure rainfall at 1 minute
209 intervals. Total rainfall and intensity (maximum rainfall intensity in 30 minutes, I_{30})
210 were computed for each event leading to runoff collection. Based on the product of total
211 rainfall and I_{30} (mm mmh^{-1}) as a measure of rainfall erosivity (Martínez-Mena et al.,
212 1998, 2001), the events were divided into i) class 1, where $P^* I_{30} < 160$, ii) class 2,
213 where $160 < P^* I_{30} > 400$ and iii) class 3, where $P^* I_{30} > 400$. Class 1, 2 and 3 correspond,
214 respectively, to i) low amount (average of 11.57 ± 1.63 mm) and low I_{30} (5.21 ± 0.72
215 mmh^{-1}), ii) moderate to high amount (21.19 ± 2.23 mm) and moderate intensity
216 (13.28 ± 1.13 mmh^{-1}) and iii) high amount (36 ± 7.21 mm) and high intensity (20 ± 3.85
217 mmh^{-1}). Class 1 represented 44% of the rainfall events occurring during the study
218 period while, class 2 and 3 represented 31% and 24%, respectively. For the variables for
219 which insufficient data were available (size distribution of transported particles, POC
220 and MOC in sediments) the rainfall erosivity was classified into two classes (1 and
221 2+3).

222 Statistical procedures were carried out with the software package SPSS 17 for
223 Windows. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to detect the treatment-
224 effects on measured variables, and the Tukey test was used to test comparison among

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225 treatments means at $P < 0.05$. Pearson's correlations were used to calculate the
226 correlation between the measured variables.

227 **3. Results**

228 **3.1. Change in soil OC with land use**

229 The total OC content in the bulk soil changed from 26.4 gkg^{-1} in the forest to 10.0 gkg^{-1}
230 in the cultivated soil, which means about a 60% decrease as a result of cultivation
231 (Table 1). The OC concentration in the different aggregate sizes was also higher in the
232 forest than in the cultivated plot. Cultivation decreased the OC content in the small
233 macroaggregates (2000-250 μm) and microaggregates (250-50 μm) by about 60% and
234 by about 40% in the large macroaggregate (5000-2000 μm) and silt-plus clay-size
235 (Table 1). Differences in OC distribution in the aggregates was observed between land
236 uses. Thus, the forest soil displayed higher OC concentration in the microaggregates
237 than in the large macroaggregates, while in the cultivated soil no significant differences
238 were observed in the OC concentration for the different aggregate sizes (Table 1).

239 Higher POC and MOC values were observed in the forest than in the cultivated plot in
240 the bulk soil and all the aggregate sizes analysed. The organic C fraction most strongly
241 affected by cultivation was the POC in the microaggregates, where its content decreased
242 from 16.7 g C kg^{-1} in forest soil to 2.9 g C kg^{-1} in the cultivated soil, which means a
243 reduction of about 83% for this OC fraction due to cultivation.

244 In the forest soil higher POC values were observed in the microaggregate (250-50 μm)
245 fraction than in the macroaggregates (large and small) (Table 1), while no significant
246 differences in these pools between aggregate sizes were observed in the cultivated plot.

247 **3.2. Change in the sediments production and characteristics with land use and rainfall.**

248 **3.2.1. Soil losses by erosion**

249 During the study period, 45 events produced runoff and sediment in both plots. The
250 change from forest to cultivation led, for the total study period, to a two fold increase in
251 the total runoff (96.0 mm in the olive grove and 47.3 mm in the forest) and close to a
252 three-fold increase in the mean sediment concentration ($1.68 \pm 0.4 \text{ g l}^{-1}$ in the olive grove
253 and $0.95 \pm 0.2 \text{ g l}^{-1}$ in the forest). The result was that the olive grove displayed a total soil
254 loss five-times higher than the forest plot (375.9 g m^{-2} in the olive grove and 68.7 g m^{-2}
255 in the forest).

256 Greater differences in soil loss between land uses were obtained after more erosive
257 events. Thus, soil loss was practically equal in both plots in events of low intensity
258 (class 1), which represented 44% of the total number of events, while erosion was up to
259 7 times greater in the olive grove than in forest soil in the most erosive events (class 3),
260 which represented 22% of the total events occurred (Figure 1). The events responsible
261 for 72% of the total soil losses in the forest and 52% in the olive grove (three out of 45
262 events) corresponded to storms occurring in summer (mainly September) and autumn,
263 corresponding to class three according to the rainfall erosivity classification above.

264 **3.2.2. Size distribution of the sediments**

265 When the ultimate (dispersed) particle size distribution of the sediment was analysed,
266 substantially more fine fractions were observed in sediments than in the original soils
267 (Table 2). The clay plus fine silt content ($<20 \mu\text{m}$) increased from 60% and 57% in the
268 soils to 80 and 84% in the sediments, for forest and olive plots, respectively. Lower
269 coarse silt (20-50 μm) values were observed in sediment (decrease from 15% to 12% in
270 the forest and from 19% to 9% in the olive grove) and lower sand content (decrease
271 from 25% to 8% in the forest and from 24% to 7% in the olive grove). The enrichment

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272 ratio in clay plus fine silt was higher than 1 in both plots and higher in the olive plot
273 than in the forest one, while the enrichment ratios of the rest of particles sizes were
274 always lower than 1 and higher in the forest than in the olive plot for particles between
275 20 and 50 μm (Table 2). The significant difference between plots in the ER of particles
276 smaller than 50 μm was still evident when the data were compiled as a function of
277 rainfall class. The aggregation ratio (effective particle size distribution/ultimate particle
278 size distribution in sediments) showed that the transport of sediments was mainly in
279 aggregate form (aggregate ratio >1) for particles greater than 20 μm in size and close to
280 primary particles for clay and fine silt (aggregate ratio close to 1) in both land uses.
281 However, some differences between land uses were observed when the aggregate ratio
282 was compiled as a function of the rainfall classes. In the olive grove plot, a decrease in
283 the aggregation ratio of the transported particles was observed for the most erosive
284 storms (class 2+3), this reduction being significant for sand-sized particles. In contrast,
285 no significant difference in the aggregation ratio of any particle size was observed in the
286 forest plot regardless of the rainfall class (Figure 2). These results are consistent with
287 the greater ($p<0.05$) soil aggregate stability found in the forest plot ($\text{TDI}=73.9\pm 3.7$)
288 than in the olive ($\text{TDI}=41.0\pm 7.7$) plot, the former needing higher thresholds of rainfall
289 depth and intensity before the aggregates were broken up.

290 **3.2.3. Forms of organic carbon in sediments**

291 Higher values in sediment carbon concentration were observed in the forest plot, (with
292 an average of $57.3\pm 3.1\text{ g C kg}^{-1}$), than in the olive plot (with an average of $31.0\pm 2.2\text{ g C}$
293 kg^{-1}) for the analysed period (Figure 1). However, the average OC enrichment ratios of
294 the sediments (ER_{OC}) was higher in the olive (2.88 ± 0.21) than in the forest (2.21 ± 0.12)
295 plot at $p<0.05$, and they were above 1 for all the events and plots.

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296 A positive correlation between P*I30 and OC concentration in sediments ($r=0.54$,
297 $p<0.01$) and P*I30 and OC enrichment ratios ($r=0.43$, $p<0.05$) was observed for the
298 forest plot. The concentration of carbon in sediment was 1.4 times higher in this plot
299 (Figure 1). No correlation was observed between sediment OC concentration and ER_{OC}
300 ratios and the rainfall characteristics in the olive plot. The difference in the ER_{OC}
301 between both land uses was higher for low intensity events (OC enrichment ratios 1.6
302 higher in olive than in forest soil) (class 1), than for medium and high intensity events
303 (class 2 and 3), where the OC enrichment ratios were slightly higher but not
304 significantly different between both plots (Figure 1).

305 Analysis of the OC pools in the sediment for 10 events displayed higher mean values in
306 the forest plot for both OC fractions: MOC and POC (Table 3) than in the olive plot.
307 Although no differences were observed in the POC (ER_{POC}) or in the MOC (ER_{MOC})
308 enrichment ratios between land uses, the average ER_{POC}/ER_{MOC} ratio was higher in the
309 olive plot (1.16 ± 0.21) than in the forest, with average values lower than 1 (0.65 ± 0.07)
310 for the analysed events (Table 3). Due to the lack of correlation between rainfall
311 characteristics and the type of mobilized OC pool in the plots, all data were analysed
312 together.

313 The labile carbon represented a small percentage of the total OC observed in sediments
314 and was similar in both plots (14.8 ± 1.4 % in the forest and 12.3 ± 1.8 % in the olive
315 plot).

316 **4. Discussion**

317 The reduction observed in the total OC in the soil with conversion from forest to
318 cultivated observed in this study is in agreement with other studies. Ellert & Gregorich,
319 (1996) found a 34% loss of C and De Gryze et al., (2004) and Boix-Fayos et al., (2009)
320 showed reduction of soil C by 60% at 0-7 cm depth and 0-5 cm, respectively.

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321 In both plots sediments are enriched in OC compared with the soil where they originally
322 came from, as is usual in many soils (Palis et al., 1997, Starr et al., 2000, Bertol et al.,
323 2007, Owens et al., 2002, Girmany et al., 2009). This reflects the selectivity of erosion
324 processes as regards to OC. This selectivity has been attributed, partly, to the fine-sized
325 sediments transported by runoff, which in general, are richer in silt and, specially, clay
326 particles than the bulk soil from which the sediments were removed. Similar
327 enrichment values than those obtained in this study for $< 20 \mu\text{m}$ particles and depletion
328 values for $> 50 \mu\text{m}$ particles were obtained by several authors for soils with more than
329 70% silt (Rhoton et al., 1979, Jin, et al., 2009). The sediment of the cultivated plot was
330 richer in clay plus fine-silt than the forest plot, which may explain the differences found
331 in the enrichment ratios values between both plots ($ER_{\text{CFS}}=1.8$ in the olive grove and
332 1.3 in the forest) (Table 2). Similar results were obtained by other authors, who found
333 higher clay enrichment ratios in plots without vegetation than in those with vegetation,
334 which suggest that cover may influence ER and thus carbon enrichment (Schiettecatte et
335 al., 2008).

336 Different relations between rainfall characteristics and ER_{OC} were found in both plots
337 which may be due to the effect that vegetation has on some soil characteristics and on
338 OC mobilization and transport through the plot (Polyakov and Lal, 2004, Girmany et
339 al., 2009). Vegetation cover in the forest plot has the effect of buffering the soil from
340 raindrop impact and dissipating the energy of the runoff, as has been observed in other
341 areas of the region (Martínez-Mena et al., 1999). Furthermore, the higher soil aggregate
342 stability found in this plot meant more energy was needed to release C from the more
343 stable aggregates compared with the olive plot. In fact, in the olive plot low-intensity
344 storms were sufficient to detach the less resistant soil aggregates and release the
345 associated C, and there was a possibility of CO_2 emission during the transport of

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346 particles and/or in the deposited sediment (Figure 2). The lack of correlation between
347 ER_{OC} and rainfall in olive plot may also be due to the fact that with intensive soil
348 erosion and high sediment removal, the low fertility subsoil is mixed with top soil,
349 reducing the overall nutrient and OC concentration of the eroded sediment (Palis et al.,
350 1994, Marston, 1989, Bajracharya et al., 1998, Schiettecatte et al., 2008). In fact, a
351 negative trend was observed in the olive plot between the concentration of OC in
352 sediment and total soil loss. The opposite behaviour was observed in the forest plot
353 where there was a positive correlation between total erosion and OC concentration in
354 the sediment ($r=0.364$, $p<0.005$).

355 The effect of rainfall erosivity on carbon mobilization was different in both plots. The
356 difference found in C distribution among the different aggregate sizes may help explain
357 those differences. Thus, in the olive plot, homogeneous distribution of soil OC within
358 aggregate sizes may indicate that, regardless of the aggregate sizes transported by
359 erosion in the different events, the associated carbon in them is similar.

360 The difference found between plots as regards C distribution among the different
361 aggregate sizes, has been obtained by other authors (Beare et al., (1994) and Piccolo et
362 al., (2004), Bongiovanni & Lobartini, 2006),

363 As regards the form of C transported in the sediments in our study site, the average
364 ER_{POC}/ER_{MOC} ratio for the events analysed was lower than 1 in the forest plot and
365 higher than 1 in the olive plot, indicating that more labile carbon is lost through erosion
366 in the cultivated area (Table 3).

367 The higher average losses of POC, in comparison to stable carbon, in the olive plot is
368 consistent with the results obtained by other authors, who mentioned that there is a
369 preferential transport of POC in sediments due to its low density, which is one of the
370 major causes of SOC enrichment during erosion (Polyakov and Lal, 2008). The highest

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371 values of ER_{OC} in low intensity storms in the olive plot suggest that POC is
372 preferentially moved in these events, where transport capacity is low. In contrast, more
373 stable organic carbon will probably be transported in high intensity events: in aggregate
374 form with a greater probability of being sequestered in the sediment (aggregates smaller
375 than 20 μm) or in particulate form (after the rupture of aggregates) with a greater
376 probability of mineralization.

377 The higher POC values observed in the soil microaggregate fraction than in the
378 macroaggregates in the forest plot is consistent with the lower ER_{POC} observed in this
379 plot comparing to the olive grove suggesting that microaggregates physically protect
380 particulate C and underlining the importance of the microaggregates for C sequestration
381 (De Gryze et al., 2004).

382 Comparing to the ER_{oc} values, the ER_{POC} values in sediment obtained for both plots are
383 quite different than other finding mentioned in the literature, where the enrichment
384 ratios of the ER_{POC} , and thus the potential labile carbon in sediments, is up to 18 times
385 higher than the ER_{OC} (Jacinthe et al., 2004). The available data (Jacinthe et al., 2002,
386 West and Wali, 2002) although scarce, suggest that shortly after an erosion event the
387 SOC mineralization rate in the sediment is substantial. Several authors have quantified
388 these mineralization rates and pointed to a 10-60% increase in CO_2 emission from
389 various soils after aggregate breakdown (Franzluebbers, 1999). Rodríguez et al., (2004),
390 found that the most labile OC forms (probably as particulate or free OC) represented
391 only a small percentage of eroded carbon and to explain the high nonpyrophosphate-
392 extractable forms (stable OC) found in the eroded OC in Andosols, these authors
393 implied that the mineralization of SOC removed by sheet water erosion can be an
394 important source of atmospheric CO_2 . Further studies are necessary in these

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395 Mediterranean areas to know the extent of OC mineralization during the two steps of
396 the erosion process: transport and deposition.

397 Different behaviour was observed between ER_{OC} , total OC losses in sediment and
398 rainfall classes. Thus, ER_{OC} was higher in the olive than in the forest plot during events
399 of low rainfall erosivity (class 1), which represented almost 50% of the total events in
400 this area. However, the differences between plots in the total amount of mobilized
401 organic carbon was higher in the olive during high rainfall erosivity events displaying
402 up to three times more mobilized carbon than the forest one, which was related to the
403 greater sediment production observed in the former (Figure 1).

404 **Conclusions**

405 Both low and high intensity events play an important role in the C lost through erosion
406 when land use change from forest to cultivated land is done. Low amount and intensity
407 rainfall is important for removing nutrient-rich sediment, while intense rainfall events
408 transport a larger quantity of sediment and so total OC in cultivated land than in forest
409 land. Furthermore, from the point of view of the total carbon lost through erosion,
410 intensity rainfall is critical in these semi-arid areas where, as in this study, two or three
411 events are the main contributors to total carbon export. These results suggest that the
412 amount of sediment lost rather than SOC concentration is the main cause of SOC loss
413 and so the mechanism of soil C loss through erosion is determined by three key factors:
414 the distribution of OC pools in soil aggregates, rainfall kinetic energy and the structural
415 stability of the soil. This should be taken into account when using models to predict the
416 impact of erosion-induced C loss.

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Table 1. Organic carbon (OC), mineral-associated organic carbon (MOC), particulate organic carbon (POC) concentration (g kg^{-1}) in bulk soil and aggregates from forest and olive sites. Data represent % aggregate fraction.

Aggregate sizes (μm)	Forest			Olive		
	OC	MOC	POC	OC	MOC	POC
5000-2000	17.3 \pm 0.4 ^{ab}	12.9 \pm 0.04 ^{ab}	8.0 \pm 1.3 ^{ab}	10.2 \pm 0.4 ^{aa}	7.6 \pm 0.6 ^{aa}	2.0 \pm 0.2 ^{aa}
2000-250	25.1 \pm 2.2 ^{abB}	16.4 \pm 0.15 ^{bb}	7.6 \pm 1.1 ^{ab}	10.3 \pm 0.5 ^{aa}	6.0 \pm 0.4 ^{aa}	2.1 \pm 0.9 ^{aa}
250-50	31.2 \pm 3.9 ^{bb}	10.9 \pm 0.04 ^{ab}	16.7 \pm 1.2 ^{bb}	12.5 \pm 0.6 ^{aa}	8.3 \pm 0.4 ^{aA}	2.9 \pm 0.3 ^{aa}
<50	24.5 \pm 2.5 ^{abb}			13.3 \pm 0.5 ^{aa}		
< 2000	26.4 \pm 1.0 ^B	19.2 \pm 1.0 ^B	4.9 \pm 1.5 ^B	10.0 \pm 0.4 ^A	9.6 \pm 0.3 ^A	1.2 \pm 0.2 ^A

Mean \pm standard error. Different lower case letters in each column mean differences in the carbon content for different aggregate sizes within each land use. Different upper case letters in each row mean differences between land uses according to Tukey test at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. Enrichment ratio of primary particles in sediment

µm	Forest			Olive		
	Rainfall Class 1 (n=6)	Rainfall Class 2+3 (n=11)	All cases	Rainfall Class 1 (n=6)	Rainfall Class 2+3 (n=11)	All cases
< 2	1.52 ^{ba}	1.30 ^{aa}	1.39 ^A	1.56 ^{aa}	1.67 ^{ab}	1.63 ^B
2-20	1.30 ^{aa}	1.31 ^{aa}	1.34 ^A	1.46 ^{ab}	1.41 ^{ab}	1.40 ^B
< 20	1.39 ^{aa}	1.33 ^{aa}	1.35 ^A	1.80 ^{ab}	1.80 ^{ab}	1.81 ^B
20-50	0.71 ^{ab}	0.78 ^{ab}	0.76 ^A	0.45 ^{aa}	0.48 ^{aa}	0.47 ^B
50-250	0.46 ^{aa}	0.54 ^{aa}	0.50 ^A	0.46 ^{aa}	0.32 ^{aa}	0.37 ^A
250-2000	0.002 ^{aa}	0.09 ^{aa}	0.06 ^A	0.14 ^{aa}	0.04 ^{aa}	0.07 ^A

Different lower case letters in each column mean differences in the enrichment ratio for different rainfall class within each land use. Different upper case letters in each row mean differences between land uses according to Tukey test at $p < 0.05$.

Table 3. Forms of OC in sediment in each land use.

	$\frac{\text{POC}}{(\text{g kg}^{-1})}$	ER _{POC}	MOC (g kg ⁻¹)	ER _{MOC}	ER _{POC} /ER _{MOC}
Forest	7.3±0.8 ^A	1.5±0.2 ^A	41.0±2.5 ^A	2.1±0.1 ^A	0.6±0.1 ^A
Olive	2.2±0.3 ^B	1.9±0.3 ^A	17.7±2.9 ^B	1.8±0.3 ^A	1.2±0.2 ^B

Different letters in each column means differences between land uses according to Tukey test and at p<0.05.

Figure

Figure 1. (A) Runoff (mm), (B) erosion (g m⁻²), (C) OC in sediments (g kg⁻¹), (D) enrichment of OC in sediment and (E) total OC in sediments (g m⁻²) under different rainfall class (mm mmh⁻¹) and land uses. Different lower letters means differences between land uses within each rainfall class at p < 0.05 according to Tukey test.

Figure

Figure 2. Effective (undispersed) /ultimate (dispersed) for different aggregate sizes in Forest (A) and Olive (B) plots under different rainfall classes. Different lower letters means differences between rainfall class in the effective/ultimate sized ratio at $p < 0.05$ according to Tukey test.